

Satisfaction Towards Nightclub at Raipur Chhattisgarh

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ABSTRACT:

The objective of the study was to Customer satisfaction in Nightclub plays the important Role in Raipur Chhattisgarh, in the busy life style every young and old people are continuously facing a lot of stress other than the job , that is why the subject of Customer Satisfaction is gained attention in Raipur, the study was done asses the customer satisfaction and services of Nightclub worker and associated with different dimensional variable in customer satisfaction and services of Nightclub in Raipur. The data was collected using Customer Satisfaction Survey questionnaire & analysed using SPSS-9, level of Customer satisfaction is measure in Five-Point Likert's scale rating and Chi-Square. the result of the study showed that Most of the respondents are young and energetic and they are satisfied with Nightclub services their ambience, music and the environment. the customer mostly visited in two area like are in Nightclub Titoss and tequila.

KEYWORDS:

Customer Preference, Nightclub, Satisfaction Survey, Raipur.

INTRODUCTION :

A discothèque is an entertaining place or club where the recorded music played by "Discaires" (Disc jockeys) through the technology named as a PA system. Nightclub does not have an on-stage band but a music system with recorded loud music. Nightclub word is derived from the French word discothèque (a type of nightclub). Previously, most bars and nightclubs used live bands as entertainment. Nightclub mainly comprises of a disco floor, bar spot, lightshow, and a stage for a person known as disc jockey where he/she plays recorded song or music. Nightclubs have bouncers at the entry point and inside the theque, where they usually do not admit people with informal clothing and they look that nothing goes wrong in terms of maintaining the discipline of the Nightclub. They have the power to restrict entry to the club and remove people. For legal purpose, bouncers check ID to ensure the person is of legal drinking age and that they are not intoxicated already. The busiest nights are Friday and Saturday and most of them cater to certain music genres, such as house music or hip hop. Entering a Nightclub, requires a cover charge and it varies with factors such as special guests, early arrivals, married couple and so on and sometimes they get free entrance also.

LITERATURE REVIEW:**Biotechnology and the four pillars of food security**

Gudeta (2017) explored job satisfaction across selected demographic variables among hospital health workers in Ethiopia. The study demonstrated that age, gender, educational level, and years of experience significantly influenced job satisfaction. Younger employees and those with fewer years of service reported lower satisfaction, primarily due to workload stress and limited promotional opportunities.

Spector (2017) contributed significantly to the measurement of job satisfaction through the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS), which assesses satisfaction across multiple dimensions such as pay, promotion, supervision, fringe benefits, contingent rewards, operating conditions, coworkers, nature of work, and communication. The multidimensional approach of JSS has been widely adopted in healthcare research, allowing scholars to capture the complexity of satisfaction among nurses, doctors, and allied health professionals.

Jahan (2016), through the Human Development Report, emphasized that human development and workforce well-being are closely interconnected. The report suggested that improving job satisfaction in essential services such as healthcare is vital for sustainable development, equity, and improved population health outcomes.

Atif, Khan, and Maqbool (2015) examined job satisfaction among doctors in a tertiary care hospital in Lahore and identified it as a multi-faceted construct. Their findings indicated that

factors such as workload, remuneration, administrative support, and work-life balance strongly affected doctors' satisfaction levels. The study underscored that dissatisfaction among doctors could adversely affect patient care quality and organizational efficiency.

Abdullah et al. (2014) critically reviewed the health workforce crisis in Pakistan and highlighted job dissatisfaction as a major contributor to staff shortages, migration, and brain drain. The study emphasized that poor working environments, low salaries, lack of training opportunities, and weak governance structures significantly reduced job satisfaction among healthcare professionals.

Nikic et al. (2008) investigated job satisfaction among healthcare workers and found that satisfaction levels varied significantly based on professional role, workload, and organizational climate. The study revealed that inadequate resources, limited career advancement, and poor working conditions were major sources of dissatisfaction, whereas interpersonal relationships and professional autonomy contributed positively to satisfaction. Seccombe and Smith (1997) examined the participation of registered nurses in the labor market and highlighted that job satisfaction plays a central role in workforce stability and retention. Their study emphasized how working conditions, career opportunities, and organizational support influence nurses' decisions to remain in or exit the profession.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

To determine if there is any significant association between the Choice of Nightclub and frequency of visits with the reasons for frequency.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Study design

A Cross-sectional study using Non-Probabilistic Convenience Sampling and Random Sampling was conducted in two of the Nightclubs in Raipur Chhattisgarh. There are many Nightclubs in Raipur. Our study focused on the two mostly visited Nightclubs. They are: Titoss and Tequila. We have observed that with the similarity in spending patterns there is a huge difference in the number of customers visiting both the outlets and the focus of our study was to determine what the factors responsible for it. Cross Tabulation is used to determine the relation between two variables. In this survey we have cross tabulated with the Nightclubs choice and the frequency of visit with the reasons for frequency. Chi-Square Test is used to determine if there is any significant association between the Nightclub choice, the frequency of visits with the reasons for frequency. ANNOVA Table, Descriptive Analysis is used to determine on why the customers prefer one Nightclub over the other by taking the satisfaction rating factors like, dance floor, crowd behavior, ambience, service,

availability of order, gender and frequency of visits. Data directly collected from targeted respondents of Raipur. Well- structured questionnaire was used as a tool. For sample design, target population was Youth and students of Raipur, Chhattisgarh. People who visit Nightclubs were the Sampling Element and with 120 as the sample size. For the study, 120 questionnaires were circulated and composed over a period of one month. SPSS-9 was used to analyse the data. Necessary precautions were taken to ensure that there are no missing values. Chi-Square Tests and correlation analysis was used.

FINDINGS:

A study sample had shown (58.3%) Males and (41.7%) Females and 48.3% of them were in 18-22 Year Age Group. People go to both Titoss and Tequila but Titoss visitors are comparatively more than Tequila and the frequency of visit to any of the Nightclubs is monthly (37.5%) followed by weekly (30.0%), after examination (19.2%) and daily (13.3%).

Table 1. Various characteristics of respondents visiting Nightclub of Raipur, CG

Variables		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	70	58.3
	Female	50	41.7
Age	18-22	58	48.3
	22-25	51	42.5
	25-28	11	9.2
Preference of Nightclub	Titoss	63	52.5
	Tequila	57	47.5
Frequency of Visit to Nightclub	Daily	16	13.3
	Weekly	36	30.0
	Monthly	45	37.5
	After examination	23	19.2
Reason of Visit to Nightclub	Dance Floor	48	40.0
	Peer visit with friends	32	26.7
	Hangouts	27	22.5
	Food and drinks	9	7.5
	other factors	4	3.3
Spending's in Nightclub	Below 200	38	31.7
	200-500	61	50.8
	500-1000	17	14.2
	above 1000	4	3.3
Beverages Order	Soft drinks	12	10.0
	Hot drinks	24	20.0
	Cocktail	15	12.5

	Beer	40	33.3
	Breezer	29	24.2

Chi-Square Tests for each of the characteristics is mentioned in below table -

Pearson Chi-Square	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Choice of Nightclub and age group	1.520(a)	2	.468
Choice of the Nightclub and gender	8.258(b)	1	.004
Choice of the Nightclub and frequency of visit	8.703(a)	3	.034
Reason of visiting and preference of Nightclub	13.937(a)	4	.007
Choice of Nightclub and their spending	13.908(a)	3	.003
Beverages ordered and choice of Nightclub	3.906(a)	4	.419

Interpretation:

- Age group- Since the p value is more than 0.1 therefore, we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis so, we conclude that age and the choice of the Nightclub are independent of each other.
- Gender - So, from this as the value is less than .1, therefore we reject the null hypothesis and we accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that there is a dependency between choice of the Nightclub and the gender and are dependent of each other.
- Frequency of visit – So, from this as the value is less than .1, therefore we reject the null hypothesis and we accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that there is a dependency between choice of the Nightclub and the frequency of visit.
- Reason of visit - Since the P value is less than 0.1, therefore we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis so we conclude that there is a dependency between the choice of the Nightclub and the reasons for their visit and they are dependent of each other.
- Spending pattern - We infer that the P value is less than 0.1, therefore we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis we conclude that there is a dependency between the choice of the Nightclub and their spending behavior and are dependent.
- Beverages ordered - From the above we infer that the value of P is more than 0.1, therefore we accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternative hypothesis. So, we conclude that they independent and there is no association between the order that the people gave and the choice of the Nightclub.

Cross Tabulations was performed to determine the relation between two variables

1. Cross tabulation for Nightclubs choice and the frequency of visit: From this analysis we infer that people visiting Nightclub monthly and weekly are more the comparatively higher than of daily and after examination.

2. Cross tabulation for Nightclubs choice and the reason of visit: So, by this analysis we can infer that people visit Tequila due to the dance floor whereas in Titoss people visit because of dance floor peer visiting and hangouts.

3. Cross tabulation between frequency of visits and reason behind frequency of visits: The frequencies of visits were measured on daily, weekly, monthly and after examinations basis. The reasons of frequency which we felt would be preferred by the respondents are dance floor, peer group influence, hangouts, food & drinks.

From the above data we observe that most respondents visit the Titoss on a weekly & monthly basis, followed by after examinations and seldom on a daily basis.

Most number of respondents prefer going to Titoss because of its dance floor and peer group influence.

From the above data we observe that most respondents visit Tequila on a monthly basis, followed by weekly, daily and after examinations. Most number of respondents prefers going to Tequila mostly due to dance floor followed by peer group influence other factors

Table 2. Satisfaction level of the people towards Nightclubs in Raipur

Satisfaction Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Satisfaction towards dance floor	Dissatisfied	16	13.3
	Neutral	38	31.7
	Satisfied	40	33.3
	Highly Satisfied	26	21.7
Satisfaction towards service	Dissatisfied	13	10.8
	Neutral	49	40.8
	Satisfied	40	33.3
	Highly Satisfied	18	15.0
Satisfaction towards crowd behavior	Dissatisfied	6	5.0
	Neutral	45	37.5
	Satisfied	52	43.3
	Highly Satisfied	17	14.2
Satisfaction towards ambience	Dissatisfied	8	6.7
	Neutral	44	36.7
	Satisfied	44	36.7
	Highly Satisfied	24	20.0
Satisfaction towards music	Dissatisfied	0	0.0
	Neutral	41	34.2
	Satisfied	53	44.2
	Highly Satisfied	26	21.7

Interpretation: From the above we can infer that people are satisfied (33.3%) with the dance floor of the two Nightclubs and only few are dissatisfied (13.3%) and people's satisfaction levels are neutral (40.8%) & satisfied (33.3%) to the service provided by the Nightclub and only few are dissatisfied (10.8%) with the service. From the table 2, it is clear that more people are satisfied (43.3%) with the crowd behavior of the two Nightclubs and only few are dissatisfied (5.0%) with the crowd behavior and also, we can infer that there is equality between the satisfaction and the neutral level (36.7%) of the people and very few people are dissatisfied (6.7%) with the ambience provided by the two Nightclubs and mostly satisfied (44.2%) with the music of the Nightclub.

DISCUSSION/SUGGESTIONS:

Out of the two Nightclubs where the study was carried out, we inferred that people go to both titoss and tequila but titoss visitors (52.5%) are comparatively more than tequila (47.5%). From the study it was also found that apart from the two studied Nightclubs, customers seldom visit other Nightclubs. Most of the respondents collectively (90.8%) fall within the age group of 18-22 and 22-25 yrs of age and youth. In our study it is revealed that most of the customers visit the Nightclubs on a monthly basis and influence of peer groups was the major reason for visiting the Nightclub. When it comes to the spending's in the discothèques, most of the customers spending falls between Rs.200-Rs.500 and there is a relation between the spending pattern per visit and the choice of the Nightclub.

From the study it is made very clear that most of the customers want the Nightclubs to be open till late night and they usually prefer to order beers and breezer for male and female respectively rather than soft drinks. Customer visiting Nightclubs hardly go to there for only food.

CONCLUSION:

The measurement of the Customer satisfaction in disco the ques in Raipur city will provide the good quality of service in their customer. In the study, when the relationships were made between the different variables, it was found that there is a relation between the choice of the Nightclubs to that of the gender and the frequency of their visits. The result shows that large number of customers attend the Disco three or more time per weekly & they like their environment. The frequency of their visit shows the positive satisfaction of the customer. on the other hand, the services provided by the customers will also increase the Customer satisfaction level in Nightclub and most of the customer will be satisfied with environment of the Disco. but the Nightclub of the Raipur will really need to improve their Dance Floor and Service. So that they can increases the frequency of their visits customer. and also they

can motivate their staff for frontline service and give them extra training and development to increase the number of customers.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

This paper is based on a conceptual review of published literature and does not involve direct funding or collaboration with commercial biotechnology entities. The author declares no financial or personal conflicts of interest related to the subject matter discussed.

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